

Autocalibration Approach for Improving Robustness of Analog ICs

David Maljar, Daniel Arbet, Martin Kov, Rbert Ondica, Viera Stopjaková

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology
Slovak University of Technology
Email: david.maljar@stuba.sk

Abstract—This work presents a dedicated method of analog integrated circuit (IC) autocalibration, which was used to calibrate a voltage reference with the output voltage value of 96 mV. The reference accuracy might be significantly influenced by fluctuations in the manufacturing process. The essence of this technique is to suppress this undesired influence of process variations in terms of the corner conditions of 130 nm CMOS technology. All analog parts of the proposed autocalibration system are presented at the transistor level. The output of the calibration subcircuit is a digital signal controlling the autocalibration.

Keywords—digital autocalibration, process variations, voltage reference, analog design, ultra-low voltage design, CMOS

I. INTRODUCTION

The trend towards requirements for IC design has not changed for many years, it includes: increasing the computing power of ICs, and at the same time, reducing their energy consumption and area. This means focusing on a low-voltage IC design and increasing the density of circuit elements (CEs) integration. Both the above-mentioned aspects are caused by scaling down the dimensions of CEs and have a significant impact on the design of analog ICs in particular [1].

In terms of increasing the integration density, reducing the dimensions of CEs requires a high complexity of the production process into which considerable complications and limitations are therefore introduced. An undesirable factor is a random fluctuation of production parameters, for example, the rate of semiconductor dopation concentration, the thickness of gate oxide, or the geometry of CEs. Furthermore, the inaccuracy of production parameters has an undesirable effect on the electrical parameters of CEs, e.g. the threshold voltage V_{TH} or the saturation voltage $V_{DS_{sat}}$ of MOS transistors. Following the Pelgrom's law, the variance of V_{TH} is defined by:

$$\sigma_{V_{TH}}^2 = \frac{A_{V_{TH}}^2}{2WL}, \quad (1)$$

where $A_{V_{TH}}$ is constant determined by specific fabrication process [2], [3], [4], [5]. The standard deviation of V_{TH} is 9.3 % in 90 nm technology, 10.7 % in 65 nm, and up to 16 % in 45 nm CMOS technology [6]. These variations ultimately affects the circuit performance and parameters (e.g. increasing the input

offset voltage of operational amplifiers (OPAMPs), or mirroring error of current mirrors).

It is clear that the fluctuation of production parameters will trigger a chain reaction that can result in absolute malfunction of a circuit. The second critical aspect for the IC correct performance is a change of the supply voltage V_{DD} or supply current (current consumption) I_{DD} , which in design practice represents $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value. Although V_{DD} is fed to the chip as an external signal, within the IC, it may be subject to superimposed unwanted frequency components. The third critical aspect is the thermal stability of the IC. In practice, this is usually defined in the interval from $-40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $+85\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In this temperature range, the resistivity of doped silicon (applies to both P-type and N-type semiconductors) slightly increases, which again results in the degradation of electrical parameters of the IC [7]. All these *process-voltage-temperature* (PVT) variations need to be taken into account when designing IC.

Generally, digital ICs exhibit high resistance to the mentioned fluctuations. This property lies in the use of transistors as switches, where there is the exact determination of logic 0 and logic 1 values (both defined by a specific interval of electrical voltage). If the digital IC is designed with a sufficient extents of these intervals for the individual logic levels, it can work properly even with a relatively high scattering of V_{TH} of the individual transistors. For this reason, digital circuits are primarily miniaturized, highly reliable (at least to a certain degree of technological production) and highly efficient. At the same time, they operate in the standard required temperature range. Thus, in general, they have a high degree of robustness to PVT variations. In terms of V_{DD} , they can work with ultra-low values due to impact of electric field intensity at a distance of several tens of nm (transistor channel length), which is an advantage for digital ICs designers.

On the other hand, the situation with analog ICs is completely different in all mentioned aspects. Since they operate with continuous signals, the sensitivity to any variations in the value of process parameters is enormous. A good example is the input offset voltage of a OPAMP. If the input transistors are fabricated with a different value of V_{TH} (due to the non-homogeneity of the production process), the current asymmetry of the OPAMP input branches leads to an undesired input offset voltage. Designers working with low values of V_{DD} are limited already at the transistor

level. An example of a constraint resulting from a low value of V_{DD} is the cascode connection of transistors. MOS devices have a precisely set operating point (OP) under different voltage conditions. The OP is very often set to the saturation region of their output characteristics. With a low value of V_{DD} and cascode topologies, achieving a saturation voltage $V_{DS_{sat}}$ might be a problem. Moreover, if the contribution of thermal influence is considered, one can state that analog designers are facing really complex challenges.

II. MOTIVATION

There are several solutions for low-voltage design, which together with increasing the robustness and overall reliability of analog ICs, should ideally be applied simultaneously. For low-voltage design, in addition to precise topology design or selection, it is appropriate to use so called g_m/I_D methodology or bulk-driven technique [8], [9].

Methodology g_m/I_d uses the ratio of transconductance g_m and current I_D as a reference for the OP setting. Through the given ratio, it is possible to set the transistor to weak inversion, in which it works in the sub-threshold regime with I_D current under the condition $V_{GS} - V_{TH} \leq 0$. One of the primary advantages of this methodology is its technological independence. When using sub-threshold mode, it is necessary to reach the value of voltage V_{DS} at least 100 mV. Disadvantages include the high degree of I_D sensitivity to voltage V_{GS} variations (exponential dependence) and relatively low noise resistance [1], [8], [10].

The bulk-driven technique can be classified as an unconventional approach, since provides the setting of a constant bias voltage at the gate, while the useful signal is fed to the substrate electrode. Therefore, the conductivity g_{mb} becomes a key parameter. Great advantage is the direct influence of the method on V_{TH} , which allows a significant reduction of its value. [9]. The main disadvantage of this technique is the relatively low value of g_{mb} , which is 20-40 % of the standard g_m . The polarity of transistors, controlled in this way, depends on the manufacturing process: only NMOS transistors are available for the P-well process, and only PMOS transistors are available for the N-well process. The fact that NMOS and PMOS have to be manufactured in different wells, causes complications in the fabrication process in terms of the matching the MOS device parameters [11], [12].

For suppressing the influence of PVT variations before the manufacturing, the sophisticated layout design should be performed. Proper placement of CEs, diversification, orientation and symmetry are essential. By common-centroid drawing, it is possible to largely suppress the effect of temperature and dopation gradient [1], [13]. All mentioned solutions could be used only before fabrication process at the transistor or layout design levels.

An effective post-process solution to this issue is employing a calibration sub-circuit, which can compensate the degraded parameter, and calibrate the IC in this manner. The main requirements for such a sub-circuit include the minimum power consumption and

area overhead, high reliability and efficiency, and of course, the maximum possible robustness against the PVT variations. There are several calibration techniques that can be considered for this purpose: fuse-trimming, chopper stabilization, autozero technique, and digital calibration.

Fuse-trimming is a calibration method that inserts a higher number of additional elements into the calibrated circuit, which are short-circuited by fuses. The fuse devices are made of a very thin layer of metal or polysilicon. If the circuit requires a calibration, the additional calibration elements are added to the circuit by blowing the fuses. The disadvantages of this method include the increased area of the sub-circuit and its invasive character, as the fuses are blown by a laser or high current [14][15].

Chopper stabilization (CS) is technique suppressing the influence of low frequency undesirable signals (e.g. DC offset voltage or $1/f$ noise). The useful signal is transposed to a higher frequency by a modulator, where this influence is negligible. Then, this signal is demodulated to the initial baseband and filtered out by a low-pass filter. Disadvantage of this technique is limitation of useful signal by frequency of the modulation signal [16], [17].

Autozero (AZ) is technique consisting of two phases. In the first phase, the undesirable signal is sampled, in the second phase, the sample is subtracted from the useful signal. Disadvantage is the emerging sampling error [16], [17], [18]. CS and AZ methods can be used concurrently, gaining the advantages of both techniques. The penalties include increased area overhead, power consumption and usage restriction. Both techniques are primarily used for compensation of the input offset voltage in OPAMP-based systems.

The main idea of digital calibration is using the analog-to-digital conversion of the sensed degraded parameter and its further digital processing and evaluation in order to generate a compensation value. Then, a back digital-to-analog conversion is preformed, and the parameter compensation value is fed to a specific node. It is clear that digital calibration is the best alternative to the calibration of analog ICs in terms of usage, area overhead and power consumption. Due to this fact, digital calibration was chosen for further investigation.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In the Section III, the proposed autocalibration concept principle is introduced. Section IV presents the designed voltage reference, and describes the application of autocalibration approach. Section V presents a V-I converter and its important parameters. Section VI describes detailed design of a current-controlled oscillator, and in Section VII, counter and evaluation block designs are discussed.

III. CONCEPT OF THE AUTOCALIBRATED VOLTAGE REFERENCE

The voltage reference topology is shown in Fig 1. With respect to the topology presented in [19], we added M_2 and M_4 transistors to improve the absolute value of PSRR and to achieve a lower value of the temperature coefficient, respectively. In terms of the

topology application, it is necessary to achieve the value of reference voltage $V_{REF} = 96 \text{ mV}$ with the accuracy of $\pm 1\%$ for the process variations of $\pm 20\%$. The power supply voltage value of 1 V is used.

Fig. 1. The voltage reference circuit.

The prototype concept of the voltage reference autocalibration is shown in Fig 2. First of all, it is necessary to modify the voltage reference design in such a way that so called sensing port P_S and compensation port P_C of a degraded parameter (in this case V_{REF}) are identified. The great advantage of this topology is that only NMOS transistors are used. Thus, it only makes sense to analyze the voltage reference under the TT condition, FF and SS corners. A corner condition changes the reference voltage value at the node P_S , which causes a change of I_{OUT} current flowing from the V-I converter block. The changed I_{OUT} value (that controls the oscillator) influence the output oscillation frequency. This will affect the final value of the counter, which will be enabled for the duration of an external signal en . In the evaluation block, the currently counted value is compared to the reference values stored in the memory registers. The digital output signal will be fed back to the calibrated reference through the P_C node and the degraded parameter can be compensated accordingly.

Fig. 2. Concept of the voltage reference autocalibration.

IV. PROPOSED VOLTAGE REFERENCE

In Fig. 3, the voltage reference circuit modified for calibration is shown, with P_S and P_C ports determined. It can be observed that P_S port is identical to the output voltage port, because the V-I converter represents almost no energy load for the voltage reference. To create P_C port, we diversified transistor M_4

into 3 parts (according to the conditions of TT, FF and SS). In this way, transistors M_{4-2} and M_{4-3} can be connected to the circuit through M_S switch controlled by a digital signal taken from the calibration sub-circuit.

Fig. 3. Voltage reference topology within an autocalibrated frame concept.

Before starting the calibration process, the voltage reference is initially set in the expected FF process corner. The digital output function of the calibration sub-circuit is given in Tab. I.

TABLE I. INITIAL DIGITAL FUNCTION OF THE CALIBRATION SUB-CIRCUIT.

Switch M_S	Digital value
M_{S11} (port P_{C11})	0
M_{S12} (port P_{C12})	1
M_{S21} (port P_{C21})	0
M_{S22} (port P_{C22})	1

In Tab. ??, the voltage reference parameters at the assumed FF corner are shown. In addition, we analyzed the effect of V_{DD} fluctuation considered in the range of $\pm 10\%$. If the reference circuit is fabricated in the FF corner indeed, the calibration algorithm evaluates that it is calibrated and ready for application, because the $V_{REF} \approx 96 \text{ mV}$.

If the initial voltage $V_{REF} \approx 100 \text{ mV}$, the circuit was manufactured in TT condition (given in Tab. ??). In this case, the calibration sub-circuit connects the transistor M_{4-2} to the reference circuit, which corresponds to the digital function given in Tab. III.

TABLE III. DIGITAL FUNCTION FOR CALIBRATING TT CASE.

Switch M_S	Digital value
M_{S11} (port P_{C11})	1
M_{S12} (port P_{C12})	0
M_{S21} (port P_{C21})	0
M_{S22} (port P_{C22})	1

The parameters of the autocalibrated voltage reference stored in the TT condition are shown in Tab. IV.

TABLE IV. THE REFERENCE PARAMETERS IN CALIBRATED TT CASE.

	I_{MAX} [nA]	$PSRR$ [dB]	TC [$\frac{ppm}{^\circ C}$]	V_{REF} [mV]
TT _{0.9 V}	3.715	-98.98	33.42	95.89
TT _{1.0 V}	3.715	-98.98	33.42	95.89
TT _{1.1 V}	3.716	-98.98	33.42	95.89

In the case of initial voltage value $V_{REF} \approx 105$ mV, the circuit is supposed to be fabricated in SS corner (given in Tab. ??). In such a case, the calibration sub-circuit connects both transistors M_{4-2} and M_{4-3} to the voltage reference, which corresponds to the digital function given in Tab V.

TABLE V. DIGITAL FUNCTION FOR CALIBRATING SS CASE.

Switch M_S	Digital value
M_{S11} (port PC_{11})	1
M_{S12} (port PC_{12})	0
M_{S21} (port PC_{21})	1
M_{S22} (port PC_{22})	0

The parameters of the autocalibrated voltage reference stored in a SS condition are shown in Tab. VI.

TABLE VI. THE REFERENCE PARAMETERS IN CALIBRATED SS CASE.

	I_{MAX} [nA]	$PSRR$ [dB]	TC [$\frac{ppm}{^\circ C}$]	V_{REF} [mV]
SS _{0.9 V}	1.349	-94.83	98.46	95.87
SS _{1.0 V}	1.349	-94.83	98.46	95.87
SS _{1.1 V}	1.349	-94.83	98.46	95.87

Fig. 4 shows the dependence of voltage V_{REF} on temperature in the range from $-20^\circ C$ to $+85^\circ C$ for each corner. One can observe that the high temperature stability of the proposed voltage reference circuit has been achieved.

V. V-I CONVERTER

In Fig. 5, the proposed topology of V-I converter is shown. The voltage reference output signal (V_{IN} in this case) is fed to the inverting input of the folded cascode (FC). The FC circuit is used to provide that PMOS transistors of current mirrors are biased. This topology requires very high accuracy, therefore in this case, an off-chip resistor and capacitor are used. They work as the absolute reference elements that are not subject to process variations.

The most important achieved parameters of this topology are stated in Tab. VII as worst cases.

Tab. VIII presents the values of output currents of V-I converter triggered by the initial V_{REF} of the voltage reference. Since the converter also consists of PMOS transistors, the relevant boundary conditions must be considered.

Fig. 4. Dependence of V_{REF} on temperature in FF, TT and SS corners.

Fig. 5. Proposed V-I converter.

VI. PROPOSED OSCILLATOR

In Fig. 6, the designed topology of current-controlled oscillator is shown. It consists of two main blocks - an oscillator core and a pulse generator, which topology are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. In this topology, two off-chip capacitors and one resistor are again used as the absolute reference elements. Based on this fact, the output oscillation frequency already depends only on the input current I_{IN} .

The oscillator core charges external capacitors via OSC_{CAP_A} and OSC_{CAP_B} nodes through current mirrors. In addition, it generates a pulse signal using two inverter amplifiers, which controls the digital logic of the pulse generator. This output signal is located at nodes OSC_{SENSE_A} and OSC_{SENSE_B} .

The pulse generator output is the final oscillating signal that also discharges the external capacitors. One can observe that the frequency of output signal $FREQ_{OUT}$ (and also negated $nFREQ_{OUT}$) is set by the external elements, in this case. Signal $FREQ_{OUT}$ is directly connected to the counter input.

TABLE VII. MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE V-I CONVERTER.

Parameter	Worst case value
FC loop gain	50.06 dB
FC gain margin	15.11 dB
FC phase margin	57.61°
$PSRR_{I_{OUT}}$	-107.1 dB

TABLE VIII. OUTPUT CURRENTS OF V-I CONVERTER TRIGGERED BY V_{REF} .

Assumed Corner	V_{REF}	I_{OUT}
FF	95.5 mV	318.3 nA
FNSP	95.5 mV	318.3 nA
TT	100.5 mV	334.8 nA
SS	105.6 mV	351.7 nA
SNFP	105.6 mV	351.7 nA

Fig. 6. The oscillator topology.

Fig. 7. The oscillator core.

Fig. 8. The pulse generator.

VII. COUNTER AND EVALUATION BLOCK

Counter and evaluation block were described as functional blocks using Verilog language. In Tab. IX,

the counted values from the counter for en lasting 1.5 ms and under assumed corners are given.

TABLE IX. COUNTED VALUES OF A COUNTER TRIGGERED BY I_{IN} .

Assumed Corner	I_{IN}	counted value
FF	318.3 nA	1308
FNSP	318.3 nA	1313
TT	334.8 nA	1305
SS	351.7 nA	1290
SNFP	351.7 nA	1303

Function of evaluation block is graphically interpreted in Fig 9. If integer counted value $\in \langle 1290, 1303 \rangle$, the digital function presented in Tab. V will be set to the calibration sub-circuit output. If counted value is equal to 1305, the digital function presented in Tab. III will be applied. If the counter value $\in \langle 1308, 1313 \rangle$, the digital function presented in Tab. I is taken.

Fig. 9. Intervals of counter values describing the calibration process.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this work, a sub-circuit improving robustness of analog ICs though autocalibration was presented. The proposed concept will be developed further towards a future versatile autocalibration system that will be able to suppress the effect of technology fluctuations. The voltage reference was selected as a calibrated circuit due to its importance and a wide range of applications. Based on simulation results, one can state that the voltage reference reliably maintains the required V_{REF} value after calibration. In addition, it can be stated that it is temperature-independent not only within the boundary conditions but also in terms of supply voltage variations.

The next goal of the work will be to expand the range of variables of boundary conditions. In the recent sub-circuit, so-called masking the individual calibration steps might easily occur. In other words, an undesired overlapping of the intervals for counter value, determining the boundary condition, may occur. This would mean that the system would not be able to determine the digital output signal. Another potential disadvantage is the failure to treat all possible counted values.

Future work will be also focused on the integration of external components (majority of them) on a chip. One approach comes into consideration here, in which the time interval of en signal, which was absolutely defined in the recent research, will also vary with the boundary conditions (for all components).

A great simplification in this proposal is also the topology of this reference, as it consists only of NMOS transistors. If the circuit was able to detect all boundary conditions including FNFP and SNFP, it would lead to the creation of so-called universal corner detector, which would be significant for the design of analog ICs.

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